

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF S1 AND S2 REFRIGERANT AZEOTROPES

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Abstract—This study aimed to create an azeotrope of refrigerant in vapour compression system that utilize the vapour compression system with the combination of two refrigerant S1(R22) and S2(R134a). To investigate the various type of refrigerant combination. We find out five the combination during the process R22(50%) and R134a (50%), R22(75%) and R134a (25%), R22(100%) and R134a (0%), R22(0%) and R134a (100%) from this we found out the best results and study that type of combination. A refrigerant is a working fluid used in the refrigeration cycle of air conditioning systems and heat pumps where in most cases they undergo a repeated phase transition from a liquid to a gas and back again. Many working fluids have been used for such purposes.

I] Proposed experimental set-up: Refrigerant is a compound typically found in either a fluid or gaseous state. It readily absorbs heat from the environment and can provide refrigeration or air conditioning when combined with other components such as compressors and evaporators many of refrigerant are contribute to global warming and ozone layer also for the refrigeration and air conditioning unit need high refrigeration effect and eco-friendly, so society always need to find good type of refrigerant. Our aim to find the new type of refrigerant and get the total information regarding the procedure for finding the new refrigerant.

II]Performance evaluation of R404A and R507A refrigerant mixtures-in an experimental double-stage vapour compression plant The refrigeration sector, and particularly the fluids used as refrigerants in vapour compression systems, had been involved in a process of change due to international agreements in favour of the environment. The Montreal Protocol (1987) and its subsequent

amendments meant the phase out of CFC substances used in refrigeration applications. From this historical point, HCFC and HFC refrigerants had been and are still used in these applications. Nonetheless, the use of HCFC will be banned by law (CEE 2037/ 2000) in European countries in 2015, being their practical utilization limit the year 2010, which corresponds to their manufacture deadline In the commercial refrigeration sector, especially at medium and low temperatures, this change has been represented by the replacement of the CFC-502 by short-term substitutive blends such as the HCFC-402A, HCFC-402B, HCFC-403B, and HCFC-408A which will be forbidden in Europe in 2015 and long-term replacement mixtures, such as the HFC-404A and HFC-507A, which are non-ozone depleting substances.

Currently, the HFC-404A and HFC-507A are amongst the main used refrigerants in commercial refrigeration, food processing, cold storage and transport refrigeration. R507A is an azeotropic blend formed of R125 and R143a that

behaves like a pure fluid, and R404A is a near-azeotropic blend composed of R125, R143a and R134a which presents an insignificant temperature glide and has been successfully tested even in flooded systems.

Here R22 is referred as S1 refrigerant. R22 refrigerant is one specific type of refrigerant which is the main chemical your HVAC system uses to cool your home. Generally speaking, all kinds of refrigerants run through your air conditioner or heat pump and they continuously absorb and release heat in order to cool your home. Since January 1, 2010, it has been illegal to use newly manufactured HCFCs to service refrigeration and air-conditioning equipment - only reclaimed and recycled HCFCs may be used. In practice this means that the gas has to be removed from the equipment before servicing and replaced afterwards, rather than refilling with new gas. Applications were phased out under the Montreal protocol in developed countries in 2020 due to the compound's ozone depletion potential (ODP) and high global warming potential (GWP).

III] S2 (R134a)

Here R134a is referred as S2 refrigerant. Tetrafluoroethane (also known as norflurane (INN), R-134a, Freon 134a, Forane 134a, Genetron 134a, Green Gas, Florasol 134a, Suva 134a, or HFC-134a) is a hydrofluorocarbon (HFC) and haloalkane refrigerant with thermodynamic properties similar to R-12 (dichlorodifluoromethane) but with insignificant ozone depletion potential and a lower 100-year global warming potential (1,430, compared to R12's GWP of 10,900). It has the formula CF_3CH_2F and a boiling point of $-26.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($-15.34\text{ }^{\circ}\text{F}$) at atmospheric pressure. R134a cylinders are colored light blue. A phaseout and transition to HFO-1234yf and other refrigerants, with GWPs similar to CO_2 , began in 2012 within the automotive

market. Tetrafluoroethane was introduced in the early 1990s as a replacement for dichlorodifluoromethane (R12), which has massive ozone depleting properties. Even though 1,1,1,2-Tetrafluoroethane has insignificant ozone depletion potential (ozone layer) and negligible acidification potential (acid rain), it has a 100-year global warming potential (GWP) of 1430 and an approximate atmospheric lifetime of 14 years. Its concentration in the atmosphere and contribution to radiative forcing have been growing since its introduction. Thus it was included in the IPCC list of greenhouse gases. California may also prohibit the sale of canned R134a to individuals to avoid non-professional recharge of air conditioners. A ban had been in place in Wisconsin since October 1994 under ATCP 136 prohibiting sales of container sizes holding less than 15 lbs of 1,1,1,2-tetrafluoroethane, but this restriction applied only when the chemical was intended to be a refrigerant. However, the ban was lifted in Wisconsin in 2012. During the time that it was active, this Wisconsin-specific ban contained loopholes. For example, it was legal for a person to purchase gas duster containers with any amount of the chemical because in that instance the chemical is neither intended to be a refrigerant nor is HFC-134a included in the 7671a listing of class I and class II substances.

The replacement of CFCs and HCFCs under revisions of the Montreal Protocol to limit damage to, and ultimately allow recovery of, the ozone layer is now well underway. This replacement process has been due to studies of hydrofluorocarbon-based blends resulting in products such as R407C, R404A and R507A to replace R22 and R502. Although these blends have enabled a relatively swift transition away from ozone depleting substances, it is questionable if the energy efficiency or global warming potentials of these products are satisfactory or if better nonflammable HFC

alternatives exist. This paper presents the results of laboratory and practical studies of three HFC blends based on R125, R134a and R600 or R600a which have been shown to demonstrate superior energy efficiency and in one case 23% lower global warming potential than the above mentioned HFC alternatives.[01]

The performance of an air to water vapour compression heat pump has been investigated experimentally. The main purpose of this study was to investigate the possibilities of using R134a as a working fluid to replace R22 for vapour compression heat pumps. Pure R22, pure R134a and some binary mixtures of R22/ R134a were considered as working fluids. The performance of the system was characterized by mixture ratio, COP and evaporator air inlet temperature. Comparisons are made between the pure refrigerants and refrigerant mixtures based on the COP. Experimental results show that the mixture ratio affects the COP significantly, and the COP could be improved by using pure R134a or an appropriate mixture of R134a/R22 instead of pure R22. The maximum COP occurred at a mixture ratio of around 50/50% R134a/ R22. For a mass percentage of 50% of R134a, the COP was enhanced by about average 25%. 2003 Elsevier Ltd. All rights reserved.[02]

In the vent of chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) phase-out, identify long term alternative to meet requirements in respect of system performance and service is an important area of research in the refrigeration and air conditioning industry. This work focuses on experimental study of the performance of eco-friendly refrigerant mixtures. Mixtures of three existing refrigerants namely: R600a (n-butane), R134a (1,1,1,2-tetrafluoroethane) and R406A (55%R22/4%R600a/41%R142b) were considered for this research. These refrigerants were mixed in various ratios, studied and compared with R-12 (dichlorodifluoromethane) which was used as the control for the

experimentation. The rig used in the experimentation is a 2 hp (1.492 kW) domestic refrigerator, designed based on condensing and evaporating temperatures. The rig was tested with R-12, and blends of the three refrigerants.[03] Blend refrigerants combining hydrofluorocarbons and hydrocarbons are good substitutes to decrease the flammability of hydrocarbons while reducing the global warming potential of hydrofluorocarbons. Four hydrofluorocarbon/hydrocarbon blends (R134a/R290, R134a/R600, R134a/R600a, and R134a/R1270) with various compositions are investigated in vapour-compression heat pump cycles.

The effects of hydrocarbon fraction on the blend properties, including critical temperature, critical pressure, latent heat, saturated liquid line, and azeotropic behavior, are comparatively analyzed. Thermodynamic models are established for heat pump simulation. The coefficient of performances of R134a/R600 and R134a/R600a have dramatic changes within the hydrocarbon mass fraction of 0.2–1.0, while those of R134a/R290 and R134a/R1270 have dramatic changes within the fraction of 0.0–0.4. Lower condensing or higher evaporating temperatures lead to higher coefficient of performances.

In addition, the volumetric capacities first increase and then decrease with the increase of hydrocarbon fraction. R134a/R290 and R134a/R1270 show much higher volumetric capacities as compared to R134a/R600 and R134a/R600a under higher hydrocarbon fractions, which can greatly reduce the required compressor size of pure R134a. The discharge temperatures are kept in the range of 43.0C–72.3C for all the blends. To obtain low global warming potential R134a/hydrocarbon blends, the hydrocarbon fraction needs to be greater than 0.9, at which R134a/R1270 performs the best, with cooling/heating coefficient of performances

of 5.25/4.70 and cooling/heating volumetric capacities of 4.78/3.53 MJ/m³. Generally, R134a/R290 and R134a/R1270 perform much better than R134a/R600 and R134a/R600a at the low global warming

potential composition. This study can contribute to the determination of hydrofluorocarbon/hydrocarbon compositions based on comprehensive considerations of cycle efficiency, volumetric capacity, and low global warming potential target.[04]

EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP:

It is the transfer of heat from a cold reservoir to a hot one. Clausius Statement of the Second Law of thermodynamics states: “It is impossible to construct a device that operates in a cycle and produces no effect other than the transfer of heat from a lower-temperature body to a higher-temperature body”. Since the vapour compression cycle is against the Second Law of Thermodynamics, some work is necessary for the transfer to take place. The refrigerant undergoes phase changes, is one of the many refrigeration cycles and is the most widely used method for air conditioning of buildings and automobiles. It is also used in domestic and commercial refrigerators, large-scale warehouses for chilled or frozen storage of foods and meats, refrigerated trucks and railroad cars, and a host of other commercial and industrial services. Oil refineries, petrochemical and chemical processing plants, and natural gas processing plants are among the many types of industrial plants that often utilize large vapour-compression refrigeration systems. Cascade refrigeration systems may also be implemented using two compressors. Refrigeration may be defined as lowering the temperature of an enclosed space by removing heat from that space and transferring it elsewhere. A device that performs this function may also be called an air conditioner, refrigerator.

Figure (A), Experimental Set-Up (Front view)

Figure (B), Experimental Set-Up (Rear View)

The compression refrigeration cycle consists of circulating a liquid refrigerant through four stages of a closed system. As the refrigerant circulates through the system, it is alternately compressed and expanded, changing its state from a liquid to a vapour. As the refrigerant changes state, heat is absorbed and expelled by the system, lowering the temperature of the conditioned space. Vapour compression cycle has four stages they are as follows:

Step 1: Compression

The refrigerant enters the compressor at low temperature and low pressure. It is in a gaseous state. Here, compression takes place to raise the temperature and refrigerant pressure. The refrigerant leaves the compressor and enters to the condenser.

Step 2: Condensation

The condenser is essentially a heat exchanger. Heat is transferred from the refrigerant to a flow of water.

Step 3: Expansion

When the refrigerant enters the throttling valve, it expands and releases pressure. Consequently, the temperature drops at this stage. Step 4: **Evaporator** At this stage of the Vapour Compression Refrigeration Cycle, the refrigerant is at a lower temperature than its surroundings. Therefore, it evaporates and absorbs latent heat of vaporization.

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Figure. Vapour Compression Refrigeration Cycle

In the first stage of the refrigeration cycle, refrigerant enters a compressor as a low-pressure vapour. The compressor compresses the refrigerant to a high-pressure vapour, causing it to become superheated. Once the refrigerant is compressed and heated, it leaves the compressor and enters the next stage of the cycle. In a hermetically sealed compressor, the compressor and the motor are enclosed in the welded steel casing and the two are connected by a common shaft. This makes the whole compressor and the motor a single compact and portable unit that can be handled easily.

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

The results of the experimentation for all azeotropes with different percentages are presented in tabular form and given in Table 5.1. From the summarized results, it is clear that first combination of R22 (100%), and R134a (0%) gives actual COP 2.38 and theoretical COP is 2.92 and relative COP is 0.815. Second combination of R22(75%) and R134a (25%) gives actual COP is 1.56. Third combination of R22-50% and R134a-50% gives actual COP 3.57. Fourth combination of R22-25% and R134a-75% gives actual COP 3.44. Fifth combination of R22(0%) and R134a (100%) gives actual COP is 2.33 and theoretical COP is 2.75 and relative COP is 0.8472.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion from the experimentation conducted for different azeotropes/refrigerant mixtures is given below. Five trials on the vapour compression system were conducted. From that some conclusions were drawn. The different combinations of refrigerants used, out of which following-

R22-50% and R134a-50% Actual cop 3.57

R22-25% and R134a-75% Actual cop 3.44

gives the best Coefficient of Performance (COP) results.

Results of other trials are R22 (100%), and R134a (0%) actual COP is 2.38 theoretical COP is 2.92 and relative COP is 0.815. R22(0%) and R134a (100%) actual COP is 2.33 theoretical COP is 2.75 and relative COP is 0.8472 and last trial R22(75%) and R134a (25%) actual COP is 1.56. From this, we conclude that R22(50%) and R134a(50%) blend/mixture provides higher COP in system which is best for use in vapour compression refrigeration systems.

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